

Japanese and US experience in Human Resource Management

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Abstract

The article examines the dissatisfaction with personnel in the organization, their classification, the impact of dissatisfaction with the personnel of enterprises and organizations on the efficiency of work, ways to overcome them and the theory of foreign experience in this area.

Keywords: Staff dissatisfaction, dissatisfaction, social problems, economic problems, motivation, organization and staff,

IJARBAS

Accepted 10 May 2021

Published 12 May 2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4923865

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INTRODUCTION

First of all, there is a look at the history of the HRM system, the development of which in the second half of the 19th century in the UK comes from Personnel Management. The effort to improve the conditions of Labor and industrial workers contributed to its activities. However, the only factor in the history of the formation of HRM is the needs of people in the process of work. At the first stage, several entrepreneurs and charitable workers, proceeding from the desire to improve their working conditions, created various programs to improve the physical working conditions, the working environment and the quality of life of their workers. The second stage of HRM coincides with the period of the First World War, when the warring Europe and the United States faced a sharp shortage of personnel and in a short time it was necessary to significantly increase labor productivity. During this time, the governments of the United States and European countries have actively promoted regular research in the field of Labor Relations and Human Factors in the employer-worker and industry. This has led to a new understanding of the problems of Human Resource Management and hence a more literate and improved co-operation of the role of Personnel Manager. The third stage of HRM development is characterized by the appearance in 30-40 years. Various academic theories of management of the twentieth century and the inclusion of Management in the general framework, which is called Social Sciences.

By the beginning of the 1960s. Within the framework of the general function of Personnel Management, separate branches of specialization began to be distinguished, they were formalized as a separate science with their subject and field of study, applied to almost all forms and sizes of business and to any situations related to human resources. Now the personnel policy and the relevant generally accepted procedures are used in the recruitment, selection and training of personnel, in the process of Labor Relations, in the planning of labor, in the management of the system.

MAIN PART

In the years of 1980-1990, strong competition in business, the development and introduction of the latest industrial technologies that depend on the availability of the highest level of highly skilled workers, flexible working styles (often associated with collective work) and the need for cultural changes at the national level, and at the level of the individual enterprise, all this has made Personnel Management Staffing has gradually become associated with an increasingly wide range of functions of business strategy. Thus, personnel managers inevitably began to be more involved in the overall business management process and began to address aspects such as profit generating, staff motivation, employee performance management, empowerment and Total Quality Management (TQM) in the activities of the company. organizational changes, etc. Personnel decisions began to be taken at the highest levels of management of the company.

In analyzing the principles of human resource management, it should be taken into account that significant experience has been accumulated in the world in this regard. Thus, in Europe, the HRM system and its direction are significantly different from similar models of other countries. This applies primarily to informal employment and employment of the poor.

In the countries of the European Union, there are several main distinguishing features of the Human Resource Management System, which are regarded as problematic nodes of the labor market in the European Union.

1. Youth unemployment. The problem of unemployment among young people is one of the most pressing problems in the countries of the European Union. In order to combat youth

unemployment, member states of the European Union have developed a number of joint decisions. This includes:

Youth mobility within the framework of the program and initiative "your first job abroad" for the purpose of finding a job abroad;

introduction of princp (workforce flexibility and safety) into the youth employment system;

formulate an internship program;

development of entrepreneurship skills among young people, development of motivation for obtaining knowledge in the economic sphere;

extensive use of European regional funds to finance youth employment programmes.

2. Salary difference between men and women. The bodies of the European Union, including the European Commission, specifically they emphasize the problem of the existence of wage differences between men and women. The European Union has made significant progress in achieving equality in the labor market over the past few decades. However, there are still significant differences in the salary difference between men and women in the countries of the European Union.

3. Labor force in aging.

Aging of the population is one of the most serious problems for the European labor market. According to experts, by 2050, the population over 64 years of age can account for 51 percent of the population of the countries of the European Union.

4. Low status of low skilled workforce and low salary.

The European labor market is becoming more and more diverse, this is due to a serious difference in the standard of living between the indigenous population of the EU countries and the coming immigrants. Initially, the social supply of the labor force, living in the European Union, is growing, the security of migrants arriving by this is waiting for many things.

5. Negative consequences in the management of immigration processes.

6. To address the employment problem in connection with the failure of the European Union.

The entry of new countries into the European Union is usually accompanied by the fact that the newly added countries are not ready to work within the framework of the single European space of the labor markets.

The structure of Human Resource Management in the BRIC countries deserves special consideration. The BRIC countries are participants in economic agreements signed by Brazil, Russia, India and China. The first letters of these states gave the name to this economic block, which accounts for 40 percent of the world's population. Recently, they will talk about expanding this block, adding South Africa to it.

In this informal structure, different national economies are given different roles. Thus, Brazil and Russia are regarded as suppliers of Natural Resources, India and China are more likely to act as donors of labor resources, where the labor resources of India are cheaper intellectual capital, while China is a less skilled labor force supplier.

One of the distinguishing features of the BRIC labor markets, which is common to all its participants, is the existence of a non-working informal sector, which is characterized by a lack of interaction with state regulators. In China, the number of informal workers is about 50%, while in India it is almost 90%. The main part of the informal employed is concentrated in agriculture, as well as in household chores.

The last few decades have been characterized by a significant change in employment with the growth of the service sector. The national economy of the BRIC countries is also subject to these processes, but much less than, for example, the American economic system. In addition to the growth of the service sector in the BRIC countries, there is a significant concentration of labor resources in agriculture, which dominates the industry. According to the estimates of the World Bank, agriculture and services in Brazil and Russia are provided with more jobs than production.

The peculiarities of Human Resource Management in Japan are similar to the American system of labor resource management in Japan. Japanese corporations manage their workers in such a way that as a result, workers must work maximum and efficiently. In order to achieve these objectives, Japanese corporations use American personnel management techniques, as well as an effective system of payroll, labor organizations and workplace analysis, employee attestation and others. But there is a huge difference in the American and Japanese management system. The success of Japanese corporations is often due to the loyalty of workers to the same company. Analogy of workers with companies gives a spiritual and high level of efficiency. Japan's management system Harakat tries to emulate this. Employees have a high level of loyalty to their companies, and employees consider themselves representatives of the corporation. Every worker in Japan believes in the personality that is necessary and necessary for the company. Usually the Japanese work a lot for their company. This shows their loyalty to the firm. Another important aspect is that Japanese workers in answering the question say the name of the company and where it works. The person asking the question is satisfied with the answer, because in such situations he wants to know the name of the company. The Daily "profession" of the Japanese practically indicates the organization and where it works.

In Japan, the HRM system is characterized by three distinctive features: umrbod yollash, salary and career-related position lifting and property trade unions. The well-known umrbod employment system, although not guaranteed by written obligations between managers and employees and not even provided for in collective agreements, is widespread and, in the opinion of many Japanese professionals, is a feature of Japanese employment system. In its essence, the system of lifelong employment is inherent only in the economic system of Japan.

It is difficult to say the exact time of the appearance of vital employment. Some researchers believe that this system has more than a century of history in Japan. Others believe that it was formed in its present form at the end of the 1920-ies. At the same time, many authors agree that the umrbad employment system was formed during the post-war period of economic recovery, as a result of the democratization of the Personnel Management System, with serious changes in the management practices of Japanese companies.

According to the umrbad employment system in Japan, a young person knows what salary he will receive when he starts work, when he reaches the age of 55 years (retirement time), the amount of his pension, and also what he will know. It will arrive by this time. This was the result of rising to the position and adhering to the printsip at an older age when determining the salary.

In the middle of the 20th century, it was basically a system of employment throughout life that defined the "Japanese economic miracle." The economic system of Japan not only recovered after the Second World War, but also began to seriously claim its leadership in the world.

In 1950-1960-ies, the mechanism of old age worked very effectively, but at a certain stage the task of modernizing the lifelong employment system remained relevant, since the latter did little for the personal growth of the individual. When a person turned 50 years old, he became a one-way employee who could apply his skills only within the framework of this company. In the 1970s. The rapid pace of development of the Japanese economy has raised the question of the need for re-education of elderly people and their exclusion from leadership positions. In this situation, many elderly workers were in a difficult situation, as a result of which there was a serious social problem. During this period, the claim that the lifelong employment system is fading has become widespread, but its defenders do not fundamentally agree with this claim.

The first crack in the system of vital employment appeared during the oil crisis in 1973-1978. Since the middle of the 1980s in Japan, there was a transition from an industrial society to an information society. The new society demanded a new type of labor, radically different from industrial-level labor. Under such conditions, old-age workers were deprived of the necessary skills.

The situation began to develop in this way, the lifelong employment system was abolished by the "Half-Life employment" system, at which time the employee could be sure of the inviolability of his place of work not to the age of 55, but to the age of 40. In the late 1980s and early 1990s. In Japan, more radical decisions began to be made aimed at eliminating the "Half-Life yollash" system and shaping the "free employment", but nevertheless, the Human Resources Management System of Japan, in one way or another, was considered the long-term work of a long-term employee.

Japan's lifelong employment (in any of its manifestations) is based on a national mentality characterized by a developed family business, and the younger generation automatically joins the economic activities of their ancestors. In most cases, lifelong employment is specifically related to running a family business.

Nevertheless, at the beginning of the XXI century, significant trends in the development of the Japanese model of HRM, a decrease in the number of individuals oriented to the group of independent owners and family members who helped them, a decrease in the number of employed in the field of independent labor in the period under consideration, became a unique phenomenon among it is precisely in the most developed countries that the number of people employed in the field of independent labor (primarily in the form of small business) has increased.

Thus, both in Japan and in other countries, analysts believe that the current stage of scientific and technical development, which has led to changes in the nature of labor, makes the system of lifelong employment increasingly economically unprofitable.

In order to ensure its operation in the new conditions, companies take the following measures:

introduction of the half-day Institute" temporary workers" ;

flexible salary in the domestic labor market, which meets external requirements, has its own demand and supply;

to maximally diversify production in order to keep the workers employed during structural economic changes;

moving employees to subcontractor companies ;

In the "American" or "market" approach, the management of its employees is organized mainly by the external labor market, the state of the economy, the demand and supply for a particular commodity. This approach came into being in conditions where the workforce

surplus and unemployment were high, while the government's Social Security program protects those who quit and reduces social tension. In these conditions, the technology of working with employees in order to improve production efficiency was constantly improved and, accordingly, the principles of Personnel Management were developed.

In firms of industrial countries such as the United States and Canada, a free "entry-exit" personnel policy is implemented. The process of Personnel Selection was not so complicated, depending on the economic situation, workers could be dismissed or transferred to another. When the introduction of new technologies was planned, ordinary workers would not have received serious attention. Due to the above point of view, Personnel Management employment was limited only to such supports as dismissal, salary, control, regulation of working conditions. Less attention was paid to motivational and social factors such as the recognition of the service provided, the distribution of commitment, the system of motivation. In this approach, it was considered that the success of the firm in the competitive struggle largely depends on technology and marketing, while the characteristics of manpower capacity were of secondary importance.

The American model of HRM is characterized by the decentralization of the labor market, within which each state has its own legislation in the field of assistance to the unemployed, its own insurance funds and other characteristics of labor activity. An important feature of the American employment policy is the spread of economic democracy in production (instead of a more developed trade union system in Europe), which is characterized by a significant participation of workers in the management of production processes. By its structure, the American labor market is a complex dynamic formation, in which it is possible to observe a significant difference in the level of income of workers, as well as employment status and the level of involvement of citizens in the industry. social production. It is possible to distinguish the following important characteristics of the American labor market.

1. Concentration of labor resources in the sphere of production of high technologies and in the sphere of services. In the United States, the network distribution of the labor force is characterized by an increase in urbanization, which leads to an increase in intangible production, IE. the priority of the service sector. This process continues in line with the growth of the industry, which requires a lot of American knowledge, which makes it possible to reduce the number of people employed in typical industrial jobs.

2. Multinational and multinational structure of the labor market.

3. One of the highest levels of labor productivity in the world. According to analysts, the United States is experiencing very high labor productivity, which gives the American economy a serious competitive advantage. So by the end of the 2000-ies higher productivity than the United States is recorded only in Korea, Taiwan and Sweden.

4. The high proportion of women in the structure of human resources.

5. The priority of the private sector in the general structure of employment of its population. It is known that the US relies on private business as a state with a developed market economy. At the same time, traditionally small scale business is the basis of employment; it provides more than 90% of the labor market.

6. To reduce the importance of trade unions in the labor market. While the trade union movement in most parts of Europe is accelerating and putting serious pressure on employers, trade unions in the American labor market are not so important. At the moment, the US trade union movement is not able to tell the big business its terms, so it is given a peripheral role in the management of human resources.

7. An increase in the vulnerability of the national labor market due to the transfer of jobs to third world countries. Over the last decade, there has been an increase in the trend of low-skilled manufacturing movements abroad. Thus, transnational corporations reduce their production costs. These processes pose a serious threat to many sectors of the American economy, in this regard many companies are forced to reduce wages for American workers.

8. Application of flexible work schedules and forms of temporary employment. The global economic crisis and the resulting unemployment have led to the adoption of appropriate anti-crisis measures in the management of human resources. To maintain employment, flexible working and time-consuming systems have been actively introduced.

9. Deepen the revenue gap between skilled and unskilled workers. The composition of income in the American labor market is seriously differentiated by three categories. Labor market participants with high knowledge and technologies ("white collars") have an advantage over those who do not have the appropriate skills.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), ADILOV BOTIR BOLTABOYEVICH, OCHILOV SARDOR HAYTBOY O'G'LI, (2021). "Japanese and US experience in Human Resource Management". Name of the Journal: International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 7- 14. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.4923865> , Issue: 5, Vol.: 3, Article: 2, Month: May, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

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